

COST Action CA21113 GenE-HumDi WG6 Meeting. Regulatory Frameworks and Clinical Applications in Genome editing: Formulating Guidelines and Industrial Agreements

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1. Context and objectives

The session focused on advancing shared understanding and alignment of regulatory, ethical, and clinical frameworks for genome editing (GE) applications within Europe. The aim was to identify key challenges and review existing ethical and regulatory responses in light of the rapid increase in new GE tools ready for application in clinical settings throughout Europe. This critical review will enable the development of updated, appropriate and robust frameworks that will meet the needs of various stakeholders, balancing harmonization with subsidiarity, and that offer recommendations for developing coherent European and potentially global guidelines in governing clinical translation of GE technologies.

2. Summary of presentations and discussions

2.1. Regulatory Frameworks for GE: A Key Deliverable for the GenE-HumDi COST Network

Dr. Karim Benabdellah and Dr. Alessia Cavazza underscored the fundamental importance of robust regulatory frameworks in the development of advanced therapies and GE technologies. They emphasized that clear and harmonized regulations are vital to guarantee the safety, efficacy, and ethical application of these emerging tools. Their intervention aimed to foster stronger collaboration among academia, regulatory agencies, and industry stakeholders, proposing the organization of an international workshop to address current regulatory challenges and the development of comprehensive regulatory guidelines. This represents a key deliverable of the COST Action “GenE-HumDi,” marking a significant step toward establishing a coordinated European framework that fosters innovation, ethical standards, and responsible implementation in GE.

2.2. Overview of EU Regulatory Framework for ATMPs

Speaker: Dr Carsten W. Lederer

Presented the current EU legislative framework for Advanced Therapy Medicinal Products (ATMPs), notably:

- Regulation (EC) No. 1394/2007 as the cornerstone legislation defining four ATMP classes (GTMPs, sCTMPs, TEPs, and combined ATMPs).
- Directive 2001/83/EC and its 2009/120/EC update, covering definitions and dossier requirements.
- Regulation (EC) No. 726/2004 governing authorization and pharmacovigilance.
- Clinical Trials Regulation (EU) No. 536/2014, establishing harmonized trial procedures since 2014.

Discussed EMA's 2025 Committee for Advanced Therapies (CAT) workshop from 16th September 2025 4 and its implications for GE oversight.

During his session, Dr Lederer outlined the core objectives of the WG6 working group:

- Formulate guidelines and regulatory documents for GE, highlighting current EMA regulations and summarizing the outcomes of the recent EMA-CAT workshop on GenE-HumDi regulatory alignment.
- Promote peer-reviewed analyses on regulatory issues, with a focus on safety and pediatric applications.
- Move toward concrete interventions by 2026.
- Explore industrial agreement models that foster collaboration between academia, regulatory bodies, and industry, encouraging the responsible and regulated translation of GE technologies.

These efforts are expected to result in:

- Consensus-based guidelines and regulatory documents aligned with the new EMA-CAT initiative, with particular attention to safety, equity, and pediatric needs.
- Framework documentation for the WG6 workshop in 2026.
- Peer-reviewed publications, including three WG6-initiated reviews in 2026, that consolidate regulatory and ethical progress.

Dr Lederer presented a detailed analysis of the European regulatory landscape concerning Advanced Therapy Medicinal Products (ATMPs), including:

- Directive 2001/83/EC and Regulation (EC) No 723/2004.
- Clinical Trials Regulation (EU) No 536/2014.
- GMP guidelines specific to ATMPs (EudraLex Vol. 4, Part IV).
- SoHO Regulation (EU) 2014/1938, adopted in June 2024.
- Various EMA guidelines on quality, clinical requirements, and patient follow-up for gene therapy treatments.

Furthermore, he emphasized the need to harmonize these frameworks with emerging challenges in epigenome editing and the importance of involving experts in product classification. He also highlighted the complexity of complying with multiple regulations, including GMP regulation in general, the overriding GMP-specific regulation, and the changing regulatory framework for differential treatment of pediatric and adult applications. In discussion, the need to evaluate GE

applications also under the legal framework for GMOs was pointed out as adding an additional level of complexity. In summary, awareness of multiple layers of legislation, from GMO over GMP to ATMP and likely forthcoming GE-specific recommendations, is essential for streamlined preclinical development, which in turn is essential for clinical trial approval and to ensure safety, efficacy, and quality toward product approval for marketing.

2.3. International Harmonization and Preclinical Requirements

Speaker: Dr Gloria Carmona

As local host, Dr Carmona started her session with a warm welcome to Sevilla for all participants. She then

- Addressed the complexity of ATMP development, emphasizing the importance of early regulatory engagement.
- Outlined documentation required for clinical authorization: Investigator's Brochure, Environmental Risk Assessment, Investigational Medicinal Product Dossier (IMPD), and Risk Management Plans.
- Stressed the critical role of preclinical development, ensuring safety, efficacy, and product characterization in alignment with GMP conditions.
- Emphasized the need for GMO authorization for both manufacturing and clinical use in Europe.
- Recommended early scientific advice interactions with national agencies, which can prevent costly delays and misaligned studies.
- Discussed the challenge of animal versus organoid models for safety testing — while regulators push for 3R principles, animal data remain mandatory in most cases.

2.4. Ethical, Legal, and Social Implications (ELSI)

Speaker: Dr Oliver Feeney

Dr. Feeney addressed the ethical dimension of GE, questioning whether ethical guidelines should be assumed to be adequate where inherited from previous technologies and from contexts framed by assumptions and priorities that may have changed. For instance, very broad and existential ethical distinctions, such as somatic treatments versus germline enhancements, and speculations of a future of unprecedented inequalities between genetic haves and have nots, may be less pressing now. More pressing may be issues of inequitable access within the area of somatic treatments itself, not speculation but an emerging regulatory challenge. While some concerns may fall away, others may increase, for instance where the well-established principles and values in traditional research ethics or medical ethics, for instance underpinning informed consent, risk-benefit assessments, are not sufficient for covering the novel challenges, such as degrees of uncertainty, from the clinical application of new GE tools. Given previous perceptions, from eugenics, to sociobiology, to genetic determinism/fatalism, it is also reasonable to consider more generally how social beliefs, cultural narratives, and perceptions of genetics influence the acceptance, expectations and concerns of these technologies. Therefore, some issues raised included:

- Risk-benefit assessment under (life-long) uncertainty, particularly in pediatric contexts.
- Vulnerability not as a fixed category, but as a contextual disposition (children, parents, social groups). The 2024 revisions to the World Medical Association's Declaration of Helsinki now frame vulnerability as a state of heightened risk of being wronged or harmed, without specifying a particular group.

- The increasing challenges in balancing values such as autonomy and best interests of the child, and sufficiently informed consent, when discussing issues of increasing complexity and uncertainty, especially with patients or parents of patients. This also has implications for the importance of trust in the professionals involved.
- The paradigmatic case of gene therapy for OTOF-related hearing loss, which immediately elicited opposing reactions from the scientific community and the deaf community, illustrating cultural justice dilemmas over different valuations of dis/abilities, with particular tension between, say, an individual child and a vulnerable community. In this respect, it was noted how such immediate reactions suggest the influence of narratives that precede some new technologies, potentially dominating the space for fresh, nuanced ethical assessments of the specific technologies (while still being informed of previous challenges, moral failures and exclusion of different voices).
- The discussion also covered the principle of subsidiarity in pediatric interventions, where research that can be done on a non-vulnerable group (adults) should be done rather than on a vulnerable group (children) – noting how this requirement has been weakened in the latest revisions of the Declaration of Helsinki to give great weighting to potential benefits that may be foregone with a stricter avoidance of research in vulnerable groups.
- Other areas included the evolution of the concept of justice in access to costly therapies, and the considerations regarding how to classify diseases based on severity, prevalence, and therapeutic feasibility.
- It was noted that the 30th Anniversary of the Oviedo (Spain) Convention will be in 2027, and it is still the only binding international bioethical instrument in biomedicine and human rights, that also has specific reference to genome interventions (Art 13) and related areas. Other than this, one has the tapestry of non-binding guidelines, indirectly relevant regulations and other areas, as subsequently outlined by Dr. Aurélie Mahalatchimy (see below).
- Attention to Oviedo may illustrate useful insights to changing national stances then and now and inconsistencies throughout – for instance, Germany (who found the convention to permissive) and the UK (who found the convention to restrictive) both declined to sign the Convention, but for opposite reasons (which may no longer apply).
- Argued for a renewed European-centered framework before pursuing global alignment, given political divergence worldwide.
- Highlighted the need for deliberative public and stakeholder engagement, beyond compliance, to maintain legitimacy and trust in GE applications.

All in all, Feeney proposed that WG6 promote a collective reflection on the Convention's relevance, considering its potential as a reference framework for future international regulations. Hence, he emphasized that Europe has a unique opportunity to lead the global debate on the ethics and legality of GE, especially amid increasing regulatory fragmentation worldwide.

2.5. Drafting Regulatory Guidelines and Clinical Roadmaps

Speaker: Dr Aurélie Mahalatchimy

- Reviewed ongoing revisions to the EU Pharmaceutical Legislation, including integration of the Orphan Drug Act and creation of Regulatory Sandboxes to allow flexible innovation pathways.
- Discussed EMA-level transfer of GMO authorization, simplifying clinical trial procedures for GMO-based ATMPs.

- Presented data on overlaps among ATMP, biologics, and biosimilar guidance documents, identifying critical gaps, especially regarding raw materials of animal origin.
- Emphasized legal qualification as the determinant of applicable regulation (e.g., not all GE medicines qualify as ATMPs).
- Recommended framing the WG6 deliverable as a “roadmap” rather than strict “guidelines” to retain flexibility across technologies and jurisdictions.

2.6. Regulatory Considerations in Preclinical and Early Clinical Phases

Speaker: Dr Petros Patsali

- Reiterated that GE therapies, due to their permanent genomic modification, require stringent safety evaluation.
- Highlighted risk–benefit balancing in rare diseases: regulators may accept higher risks when no alternative treatments exist.
- Reviewed clinical trial authorization under the CTIS platform, centralizing submissions and improving transparency across EU Member States.
- Emphasized extended follow-up requirements (up to 15 years) for patients in GE trials.
- Discussed challenges in GMP-scale manufacturing, cost, and intellectual property barriers affecting equitable patient access.
- Concluded by linking these issues to WG6’s mission: establishing harmonized European standards for safe, ethical, and accessible GE therapies.

Dr Patsali addressed the process of disease prioritization in the development of advanced therapies with technical rigor and ethical sensitivity. He explained that in line with ERDERA WP11 recommendations and efforts, his team and many others in Europe may adopt a classification model for prioritized ATMP development, based on three key dimensions: unmet medical needs (including disease severity, prevalence and urgency), psychosocial and societal impact, and the research and system readiness to address the disease with an ATMP-based therapeutic intervention. Therefore, this approach helps direct resources and therapy development toward conditions with the greatest health and social impact.

Moreover, he highlighted that this methodology aims to avoid bias and arbitrary decisions, proposing a logical, transparent, and malleable framework grounded in scientific evidence and distributive justice criteria. He also noted that some diseases are excluded due to lack of consensus or technical limitations, raising ethical concerns about equitable access to therapeutic innovation.

Overall, Dr Patsali advocated for the inclusion of experts in bioethics, public health, and social justice in decision-making committees to ensure that disease prioritization reflects democratic and inclusive values, not just biomedical criteria. His intervention was a call to build fairer decision-making frameworks that are responsive to diverse clinical and social needs.

Points Raised in the Discussion

- Comparative analysis of regulatory frameworks in Europe (EMA), USA (FDA), Japan (PMDA), and China (NMPA) should be incorporated into upcoming WG6 reviews or manuscripts.
- Stronger efforts are needed to ensure that regulators and the public do not conflate gene therapy with general “GMO” terminology, to prevent stigma and misclassification.

2.7. Planning an EU-Level Intervention

Speaker: Dr. Viviana Giannuzzi

- Presented an overview of the current and proposed EU definitions of Gene Therapy Medicinal Products (GTMPs) under the ongoing revision of the EU Pharmaceutical Legislation.
- Explained that the existing framework defines GTMPs as products containing recombinant nucleic acids administered to regulate, repair, replace, or modify genetic sequences in humans.
- Noted that the proposed revision expands the definition to include synthetic nucleic acids, genome-editing tools, and genetically modified cells, reflecting scientific advances.
- Highlighted that the European Parliament has proposed a subdivision of GTMPs into two types, one explicitly covering genome-editing therapies, though the Council of the EU has not yet endorsed this change.
- Recommended that WG6 prepare a policy brief outlining the scientific community's needs to ensure regulation remains flexible, innovation-friendly, and ethically robust.
- Proposed the creation of a WG6 policy engagement task force to coordinate communication with EU institutions.
- Invited discussion on practical mechanisms for engagement and identifying Commission contacts open to dialogue on gene-editing regulation.

Dr. Viviana delivered a technical and strategic presentation on regulatory challenges facing Advanced Therapy Medicinal Products (ATMPs), particularly those based on GE. She noted that the classification of epigenetic technologies remains ambiguous, complicating their integration into existing regulatory frameworks. This lack of definition creates uncertainty for both developers and regulators. Additionally, she emphasized the importance of the new EMA guidelines on quality, safety, and clinical follow-up for ATMPs in clinical trials, adopted in January 2025 and set to take effect in July. These guidelines represent a significant step toward standardizing criteria but also require rapid adaptation from stakeholders.

Viviana underscored the need for a more agile and efficient regulatory structure that allows for rigorous product evaluation without unnecessary delays. She also addressed the specific challenges posed by the legal framework for genetically modified organisms (GMOs), particularly in pediatric contexts, where regulation must balance child protection with early access to potentially curative therapies.

At the end, her intervention concluded with a call to strengthen collaboration among regulators, researchers, and clinicians to build a regulatory ecosystem that supports responsible, patient-centered innovation.

2.8. WG6 Collaborative Publications and Regulatory Roadmap

Speaker: Dr. Carsten W. Lederer

- Introduced the plan for three collaborative review articles to be developed by WG6 members.
- Detailed the topics and structure of each article:
 - Safety in Gene-Editing Therapeutics: addressing off-target/on-target risks, manufacturing safety, and long-term patient monitoring.
 - Equity and Access: focusing on affordability, global disparities, and frameworks for equitable therapeutic access.
 - Paediatric Applications: exploring ethical, legal, and procedural aspects of clinical studies involving minors.
- Outlined the writing process: concise sections of ~300 words per author, later consolidated into a unified manuscript.

- Identified target journals such as the Journal of Translational Medicine and Frontiers in Health Policy, with submission aimed for December 2025.
- Explained that these papers will function as reference documents for regulators and researchers, directly supporting the development of WG6 guidelines and policy recommendations.
- Encouraged members to participate as contributors, noting that bi-weekly virtual meetings will ensure steady progress.
- Concluded by stressing the importance of synchronizing WG6 outputs (publications, guidelines, and EU engagement) into a coherent regulatory advancement roadmap.

The meeting closed with thanks to the hosts and participants, reaffirming WG6's commitment to building harmonized, science-driven, and ethically responsible regulatory frameworks for GE-based therapies in Europe.

3. Spontaneous Roundtables/Discussions

- **Discussion on Regulatory Frameworks for GE**

The group discussed the obstacles to translating genome technologies into clinical practice in Europe, compared to the U.S. and China. It was proposed to explore formal mechanisms for engaging with the European Commission and to develop articles addressing equity and safety in GE. The need for collaboration between academia, regulators, and industry was emphasized, along with concern over the limited industry representation at the meeting.

- **Review of Regulations and Guidelines for ATMPs**

A regulatory overview of ATMPs was presented, including the "Consolidated Cornerstone Act" and Directive 2183. Questions were raised regarding the classification of epigenome editing, and the need for specific regulations to assess its safety was highlighted. The importance of tailored good manufacturing practices for these products was also addressed.

4. Key Takeaways

- There is no specific EU regulatory framework for GE yet; existing ATMP legislation is used as a proxy.
- Early regulatory dialogue (scientific advice) and alignment with EMA/CAT, or with structures and bodies that may assume the role of CAT in the future, are crucial to streamline development.
- Flexibility in guideline design (through roadmaps or sandboxes) is vital to accommodate rapid innovation.
- Harmonization of EU and international standards remains a top priority to enable global clinical translation.

5. Next Steps

- WG6 to draft a concept note for a European Genome Editing Roadmap, integrating regulatory, ethical, and clinical perspectives.
- Follow-up working sessions to focus on:
 - Mapping of overlapping ATMP and biologics guidance.
 - Drafting of best practices for early scientific advice engagement.
 - Outlining stakeholder engagement models for ELSI integration.

6. Closure

The WG6 meeting concluded with a clear commitment to advancing robust and collaborative regulatory frameworks for GE in Europe. The interventions highlighted the need to harmonize regulations, address gaps in emerging technologies, and reinforce cooperation among academia, industry and regulatory bodies.

To close the session, Dr Lederer invited attendees to propose ideas for venues and synergies of a future meeting with other events or scientific society meetings. He once more called for collaboration on the nascent WG6 drafts to those present and to their contacts bringing in complementary regulatory or business experience, to leave no gap from GE conception to commercialization in the output of GenE-HumDi. Therefore, this closing reaffirmed the group's dedication to responsible innovation, grounded in equity, safety, and interdisciplinary dialogue.